

Anion radical of naphthyl-azo-imidazole in ruthenium and osmium carbonyls

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Abstract : The reaction of $[M(H)(Cl)(CO)(PPh_3)_3]$ ($M = Ru, Os$) with 1-alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazole (α -NaiR **1**; β -NaiR, **2**) in boiling dry heptane has afforded $[M(Cl)(CO)(PPh_3)_2(\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR}^\ominus)]$ (**3/4** and **5/6**) ($\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR}^\ominus$, azo anion radical) as the major product. The radicals are oxidized upon treatment with NH_4PF_6 in dichloromethane-acetonitrile medium to one electron oxidized non-radical salts ($3^+/4^+$ and $5^+/6^+$). The complexes display redox couple in the range -0.3 to -0.6 V vs SCE. The magnetic properties are studied by bulk (μ BM) and EPR measurements. The anion radicals are fluorescent and free ligands do not fluoresce (**1**, **2**). DFT calculation shows that anion radical non-coordinated ligand is very much unstable while metal-carbonyls stabilize them.

Keywords : Naphthylazoimidazole, azo anion radicals, electrochemistry, EPR and DFT calculation.

Introduction

One electron reduction of azo compound (eq. (1)) in free¹⁻³ and in metal-coordinated⁴⁻⁶ state has generated anion radical compound. The reduction is taking place by accommodating electron in low-lying azo- π^* orbital. The presence of π -acidic co-ligands viz. CO, PPh_3 in the complexes may ensure the stability of radical anion.

The reaction of $[M(H)(X)(CO)(PPh_3)_3]$ ($M = Ru, Os$; $X = Cl, Br$) with 1-alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazole (α -NaiR **1**; β -NaiR, **2**) in dry heptane is associated with homolytic cleavage, generating the chelated anion radical ligand $\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR}^\ominus$ in the complexes $[M(Cl)(CO)(PPh_3)_2(\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR}^\ominus)]$ (**3/4** and **5/6**) (eq. (2)). The solid compounds are stable but in acetonitrile solution they undergo facile aerial oxidation affording red colour non-radical compounds which have been isolated as PF_6^- salts ($3^+/4^+$ and $5^+/6^+$)^{7,8}. The identity of the radical has been established by spectroscopic and magnetic (bulk moment and EPR) measurements. Interestingly, radical complexes show fluorescence activity upon UV radiation. DFT calculation of free ligand, anion radical and anion radical complexes show that the HOMO of free radical ligand is

stabilized upon M-CO coordination.

Experimental

Materials :

1-Alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazole (α -NaiR **1**; β -NaiR, **2**) were synthesized following previously published procedure^{9,10}. $[Ru(H)(Cl)(CO)(PPh_3)_3]$ and $[Os(H)(Cl)(CO)(PPh_3)_3]$ were prepared by reported method¹¹. Imidazole and all other organic chemicals and inorganic salts were available from Sisco Research Lab (SRL), Mumbai, India. The purification of acetonitrile and preparation of *n*-tetra butylammonium perchlorate $[nBu_4N][ClO_4]$ for electrochemical work were done as before. Dinitrogen was purified by bubbling through an alkaline pyrogallol solution. All other chemicals and solvents were of re-

Scheme 1

agent grade and were used without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Microanalytical data (C, H, N) were collected on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments : UV-Vis spectra, Perkin-Elmer; model Lambda 25, IR spectra (KBr disk, 4000-450 cm^{-1}), Perkin-Elmer; model RX-1, ^1H NMR spectra, Bruker (AC) 300 MHz FTNMR spectrometer. Molar conductance were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter 304 model using ca. 10^{-3} M solutions in nitromethane. Electrochemical measurements were performed using computer-controlled PAR model 250 VersaStat electrochemical instruments with Pt-disk electrodes. All measurements were carried out under nitrogen environment at 298 K with reference to Ag/AgCl, Cl^- electrode in acetonitrile using $[\text{nBu}_4\text{N}][\text{ClO}_4]$ as supporting electrolyte. The reported potentials are uncorrected for junction potential. Magnetic measurements of the polycrystalline samples were made on a vibrating sample magnetometer at room temperature (298 K). The diamagnetic corrections were evaluated from Pascal's constants. EPR spectra were recorded on a Varian E-109C spectrometer.

The fluorescence quantum yields of the complexes were determined using Coumarin-120 laser dye as a reference with a known ϕ_R of 0.60 in benzene. The complex and

the reference dye were excited at 340 nm, maintaining nearly equal absorbance (~ 0.1), and the emission spectra were recorded from 350 to 600 nm. The area of the emission spectrum was integrated using the software available in the instrument and the quantum yield is calculated according to the following equation :

$$\phi_S/\phi_R = [A_S/A_R] \times [(Abs)_R/(Abs)_S] \times [\eta_S^2/\eta_R^2]$$

Here, ϕ_S and ϕ_R are the fluorescence quantum yield of the sample and reference, respectively. A_S and A_R are the area under the fluorescence spectra of the sample and the reference respectively, $(Abs)_S$ and $(Abs)_R$ are the respective optical densities of the sample and the reference solution at the wavelength of excitation, and η_S and η_R are the values of refractive index for the respective solvent used for the sample and reference.

Computational methods :

All computations were performed using the Gaussian03 (G03)¹² software package running under Windows. The Becke's three-parameter hybrid exchange functional and the Lee-Yang-Parr nonlocal correlation functional (B3LYP)¹³ was used throughout. Elements except ruthenium were assigned a 6-31G* basis set in our calculations. For ruthenium the Los Alamos effective core potential plus double zeta (LanL2DZ)¹⁴ basis set was employed. Geometry optimization were carried out without any symmetry constraints. In all cases, vibrational frequencies were calculated to ensure that optimized geometries represented local minima. GaussSum¹⁵ was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital. This is done using Mulliken population analysis.

Synthesis of complexes :

Synthesis of $[\text{Ru}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\alpha\text{-NaiMe}^{\bullet})]$ (3a) :

To an excess of 1-methyl-2-(naphthyl- α -azo)imidazole ($\alpha\text{-NaiMe}$) (0.062 g, 0.26 mmol) dissolved in dry *n*-heptane (25 ml) $[\text{Ru}(\text{H})(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_3]$ (0.2 g, 0.21 mmol) was added and the mixture was heated to reflux for 10 h under dry dinitrogen environment. The initial orange-red colour gradually changed to dark green. The mixture was then cooled to room temperature and filtered. The dark residue was then extracted with dry benzene and evaporated under reduced pressure. An insoluble red mass was left. The product so obtained was dissolved in benzene, filtered and hexane was layered over it for diffusion. The green crystalline product was isolated but weakly dif-

fracting under X-ray irradiation. Yield, 50%.

Microanalytical data : Calcd. (Found) for $C_{51}H_{42}N_4OCIP_2Ru$ (**3a**) : C, 66.20 (66.28); H, 4.54 (4.58); N, 6.06 (6.10). For $C_{52}H_{44}N_4OCIP_2Ru$ (**3b**) : C, 66.63 (66.72); H, 4.70 (4.65); N, 5.98 (6.00). For $C_{57}H_{46}N_4OCIP_2Ru$ (**3c**) : C, 68.50 (68.62); H, 4.60 (4.63); N, 5.61 (5.67). For $C_{51}H_{42}N_4OCIP_2Ru$ (**4a**) : C, 66.20 (66.13); H, 4.54 (4.56); N, 6.06 (6.09). For $C_{52}H_{44}N_4OCIP_2Ru$ (**4b**) : C, 66.63 (66.52); H, 4.70 (4.67); N, 5.98 (5.94). For $C_{57}H_{46}N_4OCIP_2Ru$ (**4c**) : C, 68.50 (68.33); H, 4.60 (4.58); N, 5.61 (5.55).

*Synthesis of [Os(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)₂(α/β -NaiR⁻)] (**5-6**) :*

The complexes **5-6** were synthesized following the synthetic procedure of **3a** as discussed above; only difference is the reaction time which is in range of 50–60 h. The yield was 55–60%.

Microanalytical data : Calcd. (Found) for $C_{51}H_{42}N_4OCIP_2Os$ (**5a**) : C, 60.38 (60.28); H, 4.11 (4.06); N, 5.52 (5.48). For $C_{52}H_{44}N_4OCIP_2Os$ (**5b**) : C, 60.73 (60.58); H, 4.28 (4.25); N, 5.45 (5.40). For $C_{57}H_{46}N_4OCIP_2Os$ (**5c**) : C, 62.78 (62.86); H, 4.22 (4.24); N, 5.14 (5.18). For $C_{51}H_{42}N_4OCIP_2Os$ (**6a**) : C, 60.38 (60.32); H, 4.11 (4.14); N, 5.52 (5.49). For $C_{52}H_{44}N_4OCIP_2Os$ (**6b**) : C, 60.73 (60.85); H, 4.28 (4.22); N, 5.45 (5.48). For $C_{57}H_{46}N_4OCIP_2Os$ (**6c**) : C, 62.78 (62.66); H, 4.22 (4.17); N, 5.14 (5.12).

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

1-Alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazole (α -NaiR, **1**; β -NaiR, **2**) are used in this work. The anion radical complexes (**3/4** and **5/6**) and the oxidized species of the anion radical complexes ($3^+/4^+$ and $5^+/6^+$) are shown in Scheme 1. The ligands act as asymmetric bidentate chelating agent, azo (N') and imidazole (N) donors.

Upon refluxing $[M(H)(Cl)(CO)(PPh_3)_3]$ (M = Ru, Os) and 1-alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazoles (α -NaiR (**1**), β -NaiR (**2**) where R = Me (**a**), CH_2CH_3 (**b**), CH_2Ph (**c**)) in dry *n*-heptane under nitrogen has afforded a green colour solution which on concentrating under reduced pressure gave a shining crystalline green complex as a major product (> 50%). The spectroscopic studies, electrochemistry and EPR data have identified the green compounds as the azo-anion radical complexes (**3-6**). The choice of dry high boiling hydrocarbon solvent is crucial for the synthesis of radical complex. In polar or non-

polar solvent upon addition of acetic acid, the green colour instantaneously changes to red. Thus polar solvent or H^+ is responsible for radical to non-radical compound transformation.

The coordination of α/β -NaiR to Ru^{II} and Os^{II} are well supported by crystal structures and spectroscopic data of the complexes⁷. It is logical to assume that in the formation of azo anion radical complexes (eq. (2)) (**3-6**), the coordinated α/β -NaiR ligand is reduced by the electron which is coming by the homolytic cleavage of the M-H bond.

In a moisture free condition the complexes (**3/4** and **5/6**) are stable in solid state. However, upon stirring CH_2Cl_2 -MeCN solutions containing NH_4PF_6 in air, rapid aerial oxidation occurs. The oxidized product has been isolated as PF_6^- salts ($3^+/4^+$ and $5^+/6^+$).

Spectral characterization :

Infrared spectra of the complexes show many sharp and strong vibrations within 400 – 2000 cm^{-1} and the assignment of all these vibrations have not been attempted. The $\nu(CO)$ of the azo anion radical species (**3/4** and **5/6**) observed at 1890 – 1905 cm^{-1} which is shifted to lower frequency region by 40 – 50 cm^{-1} with reference to oxidized non-radical red complex ($3^+/4^+$ and $5^+/6^+$)^{7,8}. This is usual due to high electron influx from α/β -NaiR⁻ to the orbitals dominated by π -acidic CO group.

The complexes (**3/4** and **5/6**) display band ($\epsilon \sim 1520$ – $2330\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) at 600 – 625 nm (Fig. 1, Table 1). On comparing with previous report¹⁶⁻²¹, the transition is assigned to an intraligand electronic excitation. In addition to this band the complexes show relatively more intense ligand centered transitions at around 400 – 440 nm ($\epsilon \sim 5290$ – $8720\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 325 – 350 nm ($\epsilon \sim 7460$ – $11940\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) (Fig. 1).

The anion radicals, **3/4** and **5/6**, exhibit fluorescence in benzene. Excitation at 340 nm **3/4** show intense emission at 430 – 460 nm (quantum yield, ϕ varies 0.014 – 0.022) and for **5/6** the emission band (Fig. 1) shifted to longer wavelength at 450 – 470 nm (quantum yield, ϕ varies 0.020 – 0.032). The non-radical complexes and free ligand are non-fluorescent. This suggests that the excitation is of the azo anion radical electron which is (π , π^*) type. Upon addition of Cl_2 (in MeCN) emission is quenched instantaneously and absorption maxima is shifted from green to red region.

Table 1. FT-IR^a, UV-Vis spectral^b, emission spectral^c and cyclic voltammetric data^d

Complexes	$\nu(\text{CO})$ (cm^{-1})	λ_{max} (nm) ($10^{-3} \epsilon \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	$\lambda_{\text{emission}}$ (Φ)	$E_{1/2}$, V (ΔE_p , mV)
3a	1910	336 (8.86), 410 (7.12), 605 (1.72)	444 (0.015)	-0.52 (120)
3b	1915	335 (8.44), 405 (6.78), 610 (1.97)	442 (0.018)	-0.42 (130)
3c	1918	328 (8.46), 407 (6.56), 614 (2.12)	435 (0.022)	-0.44 (120)
4a	1912	338 (7.94), 418 (5.74), 598 (1.52)	446 (0.016)	-0.50 (120)
4b	1920	342 (7.46), 402 (5.67), 600 (1.88)	450 (0.014)	-0.54 (124)
4c	1916	326 (7.84), 414 (5.29), 608 (1.96)	456 (0.020)	-0.52 (130)
5a	1890	348 (11.32), 440 (8.72), 622 (2.10)	454 (0.025)	-0.42 (130)
5b	1895	335 (10.54), 435 (8.57), 618 (2.14)	462 (0.028)	-0.38 (135)
5c	1898	338 (10.46), 432 (8.35), 620 (1.88)	464 (0.024)	-0.36 (140)
6a	1900	338 (11.94), 428 (7.74), 622 (1.93)	468 (0.030)	-0.35 (130)
6b	1897	342 (11.62), 426 (7.77), 624 (2.02)	465 (0.025)	-0.34 (140)
6c	1898	326 (10.74), 434 (7.29), 618 (2.33)	460 (0.030)	-0.32 (140)

^aIn KBr disk. ^bIn benzene solution. ^cSolvent benzene, Φ = quantum yield. ^dSolvent CH_2Cl_2 , $\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$.

Fig. 1. Absorption of **3a** (—), **5a** (.....) in acetonitrile and emission spectra of **3a** (—), **5a** (-----) in benzene.

The complexes are prone to lose radical identity in MeCN solution because of high oxygen solubility in this solvent. So, we performed cyclic voltammetric experiment of azo anion radicals in CH_2Cl_2 solution. A broad quasireversible redox response ($\Delta E_p > 100$ mV) is observed at -0.3 to -0.6 V vs Ag/AgCl reference. The scanning from -0.2 V to lower potential shows this couple while asking potential 0.1 V does not show similar couple. This refers to the oxidation of azo anion radical at electrode surface at the starting point. Thus, the redox couple may be referred to $[\text{M}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR})]^+ / [\text{M}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR}^\bullet)]$.

The room temperature magnetic moments of azo anion radical complexes (**3** : 1.75–1.85; **4** : 1.84–1.88; **5** : 1.90–1.95 and **6** : 1.88–1.92 μ_B) correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron ($S = 1/2$). Powder EPR spectra are approximately axial, with the perpendicular resonance showing some signs of rhombic splitting for **5** and **6** but this splitting is absent in ruthenium complexes **3/4** and the 'g' values are nearer to 2 (Fig. 2, Table 2). The spectra do not exhibit nitrogen hyperfine structure which is not unusual because the ^{14}N coupling constant in azo- π^* radicals is small and may be difficult to observe^{4,5,22}.

DFT calculation :

The optimized structure of these molecules are deve-

Fig. 2. Powder EPR spectrum of **3b** (left) and **5b** (right) in the X-band (9.11 GHz) at 298 K. Instrument setting : power, 28 dB; modulation, 100 kHz; sweep center, 3200 G; sweep width, 1000 G; sweep time, 240 s.

Table 2. Bulk magnetic moments and EPR *g* values in solid state

Complexes	μ_{eff} (μ_B) (298 K)	<i>g</i> (298 K)
3a	1.78	2.003
3b	1.82	2.001
3c	1.76	2.003
4a	1.84	1.998
4b	1.82	2.001
4c	1.83	1.996
5a	1.96	1.996, 1.968
5b	1.94	2.002, 1.972
5c	1.95	1.998, 1.972
6a	1.90	2.004, 1.983
6b	1.90	2.003, 1.978
6c	1.92	2.002, 1.979

loped using Gaussian03 analyses package. The orbital energies along with contributions from the free ligand, anion radical and radical-metal complexes are given in

Table 3. Energy level correlation and molecular orbitals view of HOMO's and LUMO's are given in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively.

Energy sequence of HOMO is as follows : α -NaiMe ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = -5.75$ eV) \ll [Ru(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)₂(α -NaiMe[•])] (3a) ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = -1.37$ eV) $<$ [Os(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)₂(α -NaiMe[•])] (5a) ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = -1.12$ eV) $<$ α -NaiMe[•] ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = 0.97$ eV). Thus, the HOMO of free azo anion ligand (α -NaiMe[•]) is unstable compared to HOMO of free azo ligand (α -NaiMe) ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = -5.75$ eV). The HOMO in [Ru(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)₂(α -NaiMe[•])] (3a) ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = -1.37$ eV) and [Os(Cl)(CO)(PPh₃)₂(α -NaiMe[•])] (5a) ($E_{\text{HOMO}} = -1.12$ eV) are found to be better stabilised than reduced free ligand (α -NaiMe[•]) by 2.34 eV and 2.09 eV, respectively.

Fig. 4 and Table 3 show that the HOMO of α -NaiMe is mostly naphthyl and LUMO has 47% azo, 30% naphthyl in character. But in α -NaiMe[•], the HOMO is 51%

Table 3. Selected orbital energies along with contributions in gas phase

MOs (<i>E</i> , eV)	α -NaiMe (1a)								
	H-5	H-4	H-3	H-2	H-1	HOMO	LUMO	L+1	L+2
	-7.51	-7.45	-7.00	-6.87	-6.50	-5.75	-2.66	-0.93	-0.48
[-N=N-]	1	7	2	16	59	19	47	11	1
naphthyl	2	0	96	56	9	54	30	85	99
imidazole	97	93	2	28	31	27	23	4	0
MOs (<i>E</i> , eV)	α -NaiMe [•] (1a [•])								
	H-5	H-4	H-3	H-2	H-1	HOMO	LUMO	L+1	L+2
	-3.15	-2.80	-2.72	-1.78	-1.01	0.97 ^a	3.06	3.48	4.66
[-N=N-]	0	8	6	24	66	51	10	1	2
naphthyl	100	56	2	34	23	29	84	98	28
imidazole	0	36	92	42	11	20	6	1	70
MOs (<i>E</i> , eV)	[Ru(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ (α -NaiMe [•])] (3a)								
	H-5	H-4	H-3	H-2	H-1	HOMO	LUMO	L+1	L+2
	-6.05	-5.62	-4.90	-3.86	-3.55	-1.37 ^a	-0.89	-0.70	-0.65
Ru	0	8	4	45	43	14	22	14	12
α -NaiMe (L)	100	81	93	4	12	75	2	3	6
PPh ₃	0	0	0	4	6	0	70	71	63
CO	0	1	0	6	1	3	6	12	18
Cl	0	10	3	41	38	8	0	0	1
MOs (<i>E</i> , eV)	[Os(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ (α -NaiMe [•])] (5a)								
	H-5	H-4	H-3	H-2	H-1	HOMO	LUMO	L+1	L+2
	-5.91	-5.69	-4.95	-3.66	-3.39	-1.12 ^a	-0.74	-0.66	-0.56
Ru	10	2	1	40	37	23	14	2	1
α -NaiMe (L)	88	91	98	9	13	64	0	0	0
PPh ₃	0	0	0	0	8	0	86	98	99
CO	2	1	0	8	2	1	0	0	0
Cl	0	6	1	43	40	12	0	0	0

^aSingly occupied molecular orbital, SOMO.

Fig. 3. Energy level co-relation diagram in gas phase of α -NaiMe, α -NaiMe $^-$, Ru(Cl)(CO)(PPh $_3$) $_2$ (α -NaiMe $^\ominus$) (3a), [Ru(Cl)(CO)(PPh $_3$) $_2$ (α -NaiMe)] $^+$ (3a $^+$), Os(Cl)(CO)(PPh $_3$) $_2$ (α -NaiMe $^\ominus$) (5a), [Os(Cl)(CO)(PPh $_3$) $_2$ (α -NaiMe)] $^+$ (5a $^+$)

azo and LUMO is characterized by 84% naphthyl function. Thus electron is concentrated on azo group. The singly occupied molecular orbital (SOMO) in anion radical complexes, 3a and 5a, has >50% azo group. HOMO-1 and HOMO-2 contain 38–43% Cl and 37–45% Ru atomic orbitals and HOMO-3 to HOMO-5 have mostly ligand molecular orbitals. In both the complexes LUMO to LUMO+2 are >70% PPh $_3$ in character.

The transitions calculated considering only HOMO \rightarrow LUMO for α -NaiMe is at 401 nm (3.09 eV) while in α -NaiMe $^-$, HOMO-1 \rightarrow SOMO transition (1.98 eV) at 626 nm and HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO (4.07 eV) 305 nm. This is certainly due to increase in energy of SOMO (singly occupied MO). SOMO is stabilized in [Ru(Cl)(CO)(PPh $_3$) $_2$ (α -NaiMe $^\ominus$)] (3a) and [Os(Cl)(CO)(PPh $_3$) $_2$ (α -NaiMe $^\ominus$)] (5a) which is also reflected from transition energy 2.66 eV (466 nm) and 2.65 eV (468 nm) respectively. The other transition is HOMO-1 \rightarrow SOMO : 2.18 eV (569 nm) for 3a and 2.27 eV (546 nm) for 5a. The experimental data are assigned to 410, 605 nm for 3a and 440, 622 nm for 5a (Table 1). Other proposed transitions are HOMO-2 \rightarrow

SOMO (2.49 eV, 498 nm for 3a; 2.54 eV, 488 nm for 5a) and HOMO-2 \rightarrow LUMO (2.97 eV, 417 nm for 3a; 2.92 eV, 424 nm for 5a). Emission is observed for radical anion compounds. Thus excitation may be feasible to SOMO.

Redox properties of the complexes are also corroborated with the electronic structure of the molecules. Electron accommodation at SOMO is quite difficult in anion radical complex compared to non-radical compounds. This is reflected from lowering of redox potential from 0.5 V to 0.7 V (non-radical complexes) to -0.3 to -0.6 V (radical complexes). This is referred to oxidation of azo anion radical.

Conclusion :

Azo-anion radical of 1-alkyl-2-(naphthylazo)imidazole becomes stable with coordinated state in Ru/Os-CO-PPh $_3$ system. Presence of strong π -acidic ligands is mandatory to this stabilization. However, the radicals are susceptible to protic environment. The SOMO of anion radical compounds are mostly characterized by non bonding azo electron clouds. The complexes show intraligand excita-

Fig. 4. HOMO and LUMO in gas phase.

tion band in solution spectra and give one electron oxidation couple at -0.3 to -0.6 V. Radical complexes are fluorescent.

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References

- J. L. Sadler and A. J. Bard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1979.
- C. J. Jonson and R. J. Chang, *Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **43**, 3183.
- S. Goswami, R. Mukherjee and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 2825.
- C. K. Pal, S. Chattopadhyay, C. R. Sinha and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 6140.
- C. K. Pal, S. Chattopadhyay, C. R. Sinha and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1996, **35**, 2442.
- R. A. Krause and K. Krause, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 2195.
- T. K. Mondal, J. Dinda, A. M. Z. Slawin, J. D. Woollins and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 600.
- T. K. Mondal, T. Mathur, A. M. Z. Slawin, J. D. Woollins and C. Sinha, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2007, **692**, 1472.
- J. Dinda, K. Bag, C. Sinha, G. Mostafa and T.-H. Lu, *Polyhedron*, 2003, **22**, 1367.
- P. Byabartta, P. K. Santra, T. K. Misra, C. Sinha and C. H. L. Kennard, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 905.
- N. Ahmad, J. L. Levison, S. D. Robinson and M. F. Uttley, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1975, **15**, 45.
- M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, P. M. W. Gill, B. G. Johnson, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, T. A. Keith, G. A. Petersson, J. A. Montgomery, K. Raghavachari, M. A. Al-Laham, V. G. Zakrzewski, J. V. Ortiz, J. B. Foresman, J. Cioslowski, B. B. Stefanov, A. Nanayakkara, M. Challacombe, C. Y. Peng, P. Y. Ayala, W. Chen, M. W. Wong, J. L. Andres, E. S. Replogle, R. Gomperts, R. L. Martin, D. J. Fox, J. S. Binkley, D. J. Defrees, J. Baker, J. P. Stewart, M. Head-Gordon, C. Gonzalez and J. A. Pople, Gaussian Inc : Pittsburgh PA, 1998 Gaussian98.
- C. Lee, W. Yang and R. G. Parr, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1988, **37**, 785.
- P. J. Hay and W. R. Wadt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1985, **82**, 270.
- N. M. O'Boyle and J. G. Vos, GaussSum 1.0; Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland, 2005.
- M. Shivakumar, K. Pramanik, P. Ghosh and A. Chakravorty, *Chem. Commun.*, 1998, 2103.
- M. Shivakumar and A. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 477.
- K. Pramanik, M. Shivakumar, P. Ghosh and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2000, **39**, 195.
- W. Kaim, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2001, **219**, 463.
- M. Schwach, H.-D. Hausen and W. Kaim, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1999, **38**, 2242.
- N. Doslik, T. Sixt and W. Kaim, *Angew. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 2403.
- C. J. Jonson and R. Chang, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **43**, 3183.